

Certificate

OF PUBLICATION

THE FOLLOWING CERTIFICATE IS GIVEN TO
Surjit Kaur

For publishing in
Brio Innovative Journal of Novel Research (BIJNR)

“Empowering Women with PCOS: The Nurse’s Role in Holistic Management”

Volume: 1

Issue: 2

Year:2024

Pub ID: BIJNR202440

Dr Bince V
Chief Editor

P E Salim
Head of Journal

Certificate

OF PUBLICATION

THE FOLLOWING CERTIFICATE IS GIVEN TO

Dr. Jitendra Chicholkar

For publishing in
Brio Innovative Journal of Novel Research (BIJNR)

“Empowering Women with PCOS: The Nurse’s Role in Holistic Management”

Volume: 1

Issue: 2

Year:2024

Pub ID: BIJNR202440

Dr Bince V
Chief Editor

P E Salim
Head of Journal

